

Creative Accounting Practices in the Indian Corporate Sector: An Empirical Study.

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Abstract: *By and large, every set of published accounts in the corporate world have been based on books of accounts, which have been gently cooked or completely roasted. Shockingly, few 'loopholes' in the accounting 'standards' provide enough room for the use of "Creative Accounting (CA)" practices. Thus, CA practices does not provide a "true and fair" view of the FS(s), since lot of 'crunching' of financial numbers is done, within the purview of applicable laws and prevailing accounting standards. Recently, the use of CA has become a controversial issue since there are parties, both in favor and against, the use of such practices.*

As part of study, a questionnaire-based survey methodology was used, 14 specific research questions were asked, and 120 questionnaires were distributed to the preparers' and users' of the company FS(s). Finally, 85 responses from the participants were collected and analyzed using the percentage and frequencies of respondents. The study revealed that the practice of CA is always a deliberate attempt to gain undue advantage for accountants, managers and companies. Therefore, strong punitive measures should be promptly taken against all those found culpable in the act of CA. We recommend that "effective rules and regulation of accounting, audit and CG practices should be put in places, within the corporate-sector, to forestall the negative incidence of CA practices in India."

Key words: *Creative Accounting, Corporate Sector, India, Financial Statements, GAAP, IFRS, Corporate Governance, Forensic Accounting.*

Introduction

A corporation is a 'congregation' of various stakeholders. In the corporate-sector, the principal-agent relationship between the shareholders (as owners) and managers (as agent) is explained by the "agency theory," which assumes that the ordering party and the agent "tend to maximize the benefits for themselves." Due to these 'conflicting' interests, managers usually have the incentive and ability to maximize their own objective at the expense of shareholders. Market participants have to make a decision about investing in a company on the basis of the reliability, uniformity, and transparency of the published information, as contained in the Financial Statements (henceforth, FSs). However, transparency in the financial reporting system is of utmost importance because individuals, potential investors, creditors and regulators have to make investment decisions based on corporate published financial reports (Wokukwu, 2015). To produce transparent, timely and reliable FS(s), accounting process should follow 'objective' and 'consistent' set of rules. Recent, unpleasant events in the economy, coupled with frequent scandals, have raised questions about the effectiveness of transparency and disclosure practices, especially in the global corporate sector. Collapses of large number of high-profile companies, due to widespread and frequent abuse of Creative Accounting (henceforth, CA) practices, across the world, have left a dirty smear on the effectiveness of the Corporate Governance (henceforth, CG) system, the quality and transparency of the financial reports, and credibility of the audit functions. As a result, the CG structures evolve that help in mitigating these agency conflicts (Firth 2007; Dey 2008).

Undoubtedly, the CA practices can appear even in highly regulated economic systems. Under the umbrella of CA practices, the manager uses the accounting knowledge to present the accounting data, figures and statements in such a manner, which seems very attractive to the stakeholders instead of showing the real position or performance of the company, but all these, are done within the parameters of accounting standards and rules. Even if there exists a strong accounting standard to guide financial accounting activities, sometime it becomes impossible to prevent the 'manipulative' behavior of the FS preparers', who wants to effect the decisions of the users' in favor of their companies. While on one hand, "the CA practices helps in reducing the risk of a company by increasing the share price and, on the other hand, it helps to boost a profit trend for the company." Various benefits, like ease of raising capital by issue of shares, defy takeover bids by other companies, and offering its own shares in takeover bids, etc. all go in favor of the CA practices. Moreover, the CA practice also helps to reduce the fluctuations of income/profit of the company, which helps it to gain a good image in the

market (Nag, 2015). Therefore, International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) are considered more rigorous than the US GAAP regarding the issues of methods selection for the preparation of financial reports (Jawad and Xia, 2015). Moreover, the complexity and unpredictability of constantly changing environment makes it very difficult to consider all the possible situations in advance when setting standards. Even if the accounting standards cannot prevent manipulative behavior in advance, they can curb it afterwards (Wang, 2008). At present, there are 32 Accounting Standards in India, which have been issued by the Accounting Standard Board of the ICAI (Patnaik et al., 2014).

Capital markets mostly use FS(s) information to establish the price for listed securities, and the investors rely on them in order to substantiate their decisions to buy, sell, or keep these securities. Indeed, market 'efficiency' depends on the information flow provided to capital markets, and if the information is 'biased', the markets cannot determine the 'exact' price of securities. Moreover, it appeared that sometimes managers manipulate FS(s) to influence certain competitors on the capital market. For instance, 40 US companies went public in 2014 that reported losses under traditional accounting rules, but claimed profits under their own tailored CA. The bigger they are, the more likely they are to use CA (Browne, 2015). On the other hand, the fact that managers frequently use CA techniques can affect the investors' ability "to properly assess the 'true' value of the company, which in the long-term affects the company's performance on securities market." Indeed, the "CA involves the manipulation of company financial records towards a predetermined target. This target can be motivated by a preference for more stable earnings" (Micah et al., 2014). Even if there exists strong accounting standards to guide financial accounting activities, sometimes it becomes impossible to prevent the manipulative behavior of FS(s) preparers', who wants to affect the decisions of the FS(s) users' in favor of their companies. These manipulative behaviors are often called "Creative Accounting" and/or "Earnings Management" (EM). The 'CA' is the more preferred term in Europe, whereas it is more common to use 'EM' in the USA. Therefore, the accuracy and reliability of the information contained in FS(s) are very crucial for both investors and creditors to make an appropriate decision. There exists strong evidence that the emergence of Forensic Accounting has restored confidence in the credibility of corporate firms and their financial reports (Blessing, 2015). Therefore, we recommend that CA should be considered as a serious crime and as such accounting bodies, law courts and other regulatory authorities need to adopt strict measures to stop this unethical practice (Sanusi and Izedonmi, 2014).

What is Creative Accounting?

One of the early researchers, who defined the account manipulation, was Copeland (1968). The term CA was also used in 1968 in film "the producers" by Mel Brooks. The concept of CA appeared in the Anglo-Saxon literature in the 1970s.

CA refers to the accounting practice that may (or may not) follow the accounting principles or standards, but deviate from what these principles or standards intend to achieve, in order to show a desired image of the company to the stakeholders. Alternatively, CA is the transformation of financial accounting figures from "what they actually are to what the preparer of financial reports desires by taking advantage of the existing rules and/or ignoring some or all of them." Thus, CA uses the various loopholes in accounting principles or standards to show the desired results to the stakeholders.

Jawad and Xia (2015) have emphasized the 'innovative' aspects of CA in maneuvering accounting numbers and argued that "innovation is an essential part of CA practices in accounting practices." Naturally, a question that arises very often is, "whether CA is good or bad?" The final answer to this question lies in the 'purpose' for which it is used and the 'manner' in which it is done. To give a corollary, "CA is like a double-edged weapon, which can be used or abused by the management. If it is abused, then the sole fault is of the management and not of CA itself" (Bhasin, 2013). For instance, the Satyam accounting fraud, a glaring example of India's Enron,

is “clearly a case of abuse of CA in which the company accounts were manipulated by creating fake invoices, recognizing revenue on these fake receipts, and falsifying the bank balances and interest on these fixed deposits” (Goel and Ansari, 2015). The basic motto was to inflate the share prices of the company and subsequently, sell the promoters holding at the inflated prices. The ‘abuse’ of the CA, in the case of Satyam Computers Limited, was made possible due to audit failure and total failure of the company CG system. These CA practices in financial reporting have been termed by Fizza and Malik (2015) as “the art of faking or calculating or presenting the balance sheet, and the art of saving money.”

Arthur Levitt, (Chairman, SEC) in 1998, called attention to CA practices and announced an all-out war on them. He noted that “accounting principles were not meant to be a strait-jacket and some degree of flexibility was necessary to permit financial reporting to keep pace with business innovations. The problem arises when companies are using that flexibility to create illusions in their financial reports, illusions that are anything but “true and fair” reporting” (Mulford and Comiskey, 2002). After reviewing the narrow and wide definitions of CA, Jones (2011) ended up with the definition of CA as follows: “Using the flexibility in accounting within the regulatory framework to manage the measurement and presentation of the accounts so that they give privacy to the interest of the preparers, not the users”. As he mentions in his book, “in the US, where it is referred as EM, CA is defined in a ‘wider’ perspective including fraud, whereas in the UK and Europe it is seen as using the flexibility within the regulatory system but excluding fraud.” By utilizing lacunae in prevailing regulations, CA is resorted to manipulate the accounts and this cannot be held as fraud, as it is within the guidelines, accounting standards, IFRS and GAAP. To get benefits from top management, managers are frequently tempted to show higher profits, which lead to adopting CA tactics (Vyas et al., 2015). Thus, CA is a starting point of a number of accounting scandals, which collapsed during the last decade, applied CA techniques and manipulated financial record. No doubt, these accounting scandals have diminished the confidence of stakeholders in financial reporting all over the world.

What Motivates Creative Accounting?

In the modern globalized and liberalized era, the business firms are facing stiff competition and therefore, are under constant pressure to show the good financial results through their financial reporting system. In such an environment, firms usually start using the CA practices, especially in an unsuitable situation to boost up the profit/income, or manipulate the assets and liabilities to report to the stakeholders the image that is better than the actual image. There are many factors, which are regarded as the reasons for applying CA techniques.

One of the most cited incentive in the literature is “the expected increase in the stock prices.” It is not surprising since the ultimate goal of the firm should be maximizing the firm value. Thus, using CA/EM techniques may be one-way to communicate to investors that “a firm has higher earning power, helping to foster a higher stock price” (Mulford and Comiskey, 2002). In fact, the CA practices may help maintain or boost the share price both by reducing the apparent levels of borrowing, so making the company appear subject to less risk, and by creating the appearance of a good profit trend (Amat and Gowthorpe, 2004).

To increase the ‘stock’ price is not the only motivational factor of CA. At the same time, Managers can use EM “to smooth earnings” in order to present future debt-holders with low variance income streams and lower the required return of the debt-holders and thereby, the firm’s long-term cost of capital (Stolowy and Breton, 2000). No company is interested to show a particular time as a bad year for the company; so they are forced to declare an exceptionally good year as normal year or even portray a bad year as a normal year by using CA techniques (Vyas et al., 2015). Moreover, instable’ profits may make “a company more vulnerable to stock price fluctuations and even a hostile takeover.” The company with instable profits will be perceived as riskier and less well-managed compared to a company with steady profits (Jones, 2011). Moreover, “earnings-based compensation” can also make Managers apply CA/EM techniques just to meet an earnings benchmark to

increase job security or get more bonuses (Gunny, 2010). In some situations, a few managers/directors of companies may want to gain from their inside information and thus, may want to use CA to defer making any information available to the market.

Higher earnings per share ensures a good market price and a company can tap the capital market for funds very easily. Investors prefer to invest in companies having stable profits than variable profits and hence, companies try to project the same. In a monopoly, company is compelled to hide large profits and sometimes boosting of assets is required to avoid takeover (Vyas et al., 2015). In some circumstances, where it is not in a company's interests to appear to be exceptionally profitable, CA/EM might be employed to "manage earnings down." However, the effectiveness of this will hinge on the recognition or acceptance of the reduced profit level as being legitimate by the key players (Mulford and Comiskey, 2002). For example, oil companies have used income decreasing accounting policies during the Gulf War to avoid the political consequences of a higher profit coming from increased retail prices (Han and Wang, 1998).

Authors such as Niskanen, Herman and Keloharju () indicate that one of the basic motives for the use of CA is also tax payment evasion. Practical experience shows that most of the time the CA practices are not being handled judiciously. The CA techniques are mostly undertaken by managers of companies with unscrupulous intentions in order to misrepresent and mislead the various segments of society (viz., investors, creditors and employees). Thus, the managers of the company are responsible for the misuse and abuse of CA, since in order to fulfill their motives, they frequently defy the ethical considerations, which are an essential part of the CA practices. Sometimes, they resort to practices which are totally unethical and out of the limits of accounting standards posing a threat to the very existence of the company (Nag, 2015).

What are the Techniques of Creative Accounting?

- **Recognizing Premature or Fictitious Revenue:** The CA practices often begin with revenue recognition, because of its direct impact on earnings. "Premature" revenue recognition is recognition of revenue for a legitimate sale in a period prior to that called for by generally accepted accounting principles (GAAP). On the contrary, "fictitious" revenue recognition is the recording of revenue for a non-existent sale.
- **"Big Bath" Accounting:** Big-Bath is a managerial strategy "to get rid of all the bad news in one go." In this technique, Managers write-off as many costs as possible in the current period, so that the future performance looks better. It is widely used in acquisition accounting and in takeovers.
- **Using Cookie Jar Reserves:** It refers to "over-provisioning for accrued expenses when revenues are high, so that profits can be brought down to a level that is safe to maintain in the future." It also includes failure to provide all the accrued expenses to show larger profits during tougher times when needed (Shah and Butt, 2011). This technique includes making unrealistic assumptions to estimate liabilities for such items as sales returns, loan losses or warranty costs, so that they stash accruals in cookie jars during the good times and reach into them when needed in the bad times.
- **Aggressive Capitalization and Extended Amortization Policies:** One alternative way for companies to reduce expenses is "aggressively capitalizing expenditures that should have been expensed." Although determination of the portion of an expenditure to capitalize is straightforward in many cases, items as 'direct-response' advertising and 'software' development costs require 'judgment' in determining whether capitalization is appropriate or not. To lengthen amortization periods for costs that have been capitalized previously is also used to reduce expenses and boost earnings.
- **Manipulating Inventory:** Firms can engage into 'inventory' manipulation "by either manipulating the quantity of the inventory or by valuing it." In years when profits need to be increased the quantity can be manipulated by doing a particularly rigorous stock-take. Provisions for absolute and slow-moving inventory and changing the actual method of inventory valuation are the practices of manipulating inventory values (Jones, 2011).

- **Abuse of Materiality Concept:** It includes misusing the concept of materiality by intentionally recording errors within a defined percentage ceiling. Firms indulging in this practice try to find an excuse for it by arguing that the effect on the net income is too small to matter.
- **Being Generous with Bad Debts:** Companies, which are based on credit sales, make provisions for bad and doubtful debts based upon their “personal judgment”. Thus, when they want to increase their profits, Managers can forecast that there will be a very low-level of non-payment.
- **Getting Creative with the Income Statement:** It includes the “practice of communicating a different level of earning power using the format of the income statement” rather than through the manner in which transactions are recorded. For example, companies may report a non-recurring gain as “other revenue,” a recurring revenue caption, or a recurring expense might be labeled as non-recurring. This will result in higher apparent levels of recurring earnings without altering total net income.
- **Problems with Cash-flow Reporting:** Another way for companies to communicate a higher earning power is “reporting higher and more sustainable cash flow.” A company’s apparent earning power will be greater with the potential recurring quality of operating cash flow. Therefore, a firm can classify an operating expenditure as an investing or financing item, or investing or financing inflow might be classified as an operating item. Even if these steps will not alter the total change in cash, they will increase the cash flow from operations.

Creative Accounting Practices Scenario in the Indian Companies

India is a ‘developing’ economy, where the corporate-sector is contributing a major part in national income. Most of the Indian corporations are spreading their wings all over the world, where they get lots of opportunities to go for “Creative Accounting (CA)” since all countries have different accounting systems, which creates ambiguity in investor’s mind. Thus, the number of accounting scandal has also increased in India. Over the recent years, “India has developed its corporate-sector, stock-markets and the accounting profession.” The growing importance of the corporate-sector calls for its ‘efficient’ working and ‘greater’ transparency. However, the prevalence of Creative (or fudging) Accounting, and fraudulent practices followed by some of the Indian companies hinders this. In spite of the number of checks and balances required by the multiple regulatory agencies, there have been growing numbers of accounting scandals since the 1980s. Firms adopt accounting procedures that “minimizes unfavorable economic effects and enhance favorable ones.” Thus, corporate frauds are results of manipulation of accounts and accounting ‘jugglery’ designed to deceive others for wrongful gains. Such creative accounting by ‘fudging’ the accounts is attributed to the ‘flexibility’ provided by the ‘accounting’ system (Jones, 2011). In India, the Companies Act requires that accounts must be “true-and-fair”. Sometimes, however, management ‘abuses’ the freedom of choice in the accounting systems. Methods are adopted to ‘hide’ the true-picture, and show an ‘improved’ performance of the firm. In fact, the company management may adopt various methods to dress up financial statements to show improved performance. In respect of profit and loss account (or income statement), the accounting risk is usually the overstatement of income or understatement of expenses. For the balance sheet, it may exist in three areas: the correct valuation of company’s assets, accounting for all liabilities and over or understatement of net worth. The effect of CA has defeated the ‘fundamental’ purpose of presentation of “true and fair” FS, as required by Section 211 of the Indian Companies Act. **Table 1** shows some examples of Indian companies, who have practiced CA from 1996-97 to 2008-09.

Table 1: Creative Accounting and Fraudulent Practices followed by the Indian Companies

Company Name	Year(s)	Nature of CA Practices Followed
WIPRO Ltd.	1996-97 to 1999-2000	Transfer of land to stock creating capital reserve with the fair value and using it to neutralize the effect on profit of reduction of land value.
Bombay Dyeing & Manufacturing Company Limited	2003-04 and 2004-05	Creating provisions for possible loss on firm purchase contract and subsequent write-back of such provision thereby converting operating losses into operating profit.
Larsen & Toubro Limited	1999-2000 and 2001-02	Income recognition through transfer of loan liabilities at a lower consideration.
Apollo Tyres Ltd.	2004-05	Debiting profit and loss account with additional excise duty payable to the government and transferring equivalent amount from general reserve to neutralize the effect.
Asian Electronics Ltd.	2004-05	Impairment of assets: treatment of deferred tax.
Oil and Natural Gas Commission, Mukund Ltd., Torrent Power ACE Ltd. and Tata Motors Ltd.	2004-05	Capitalization of interest as well as other intangible assets to show fixed assets value upward and understating revenue expenses.
Hindustan Zinc Limited	2003-04 and 2004-05	Reclassifying assets in the balance sheet.
Tata Motors, Bombay Dyeing, Mahindra and Himachal Futuristic	2001-02	Direct write-offs from reserves.
Satyam Computers Services Limited	2008-09	Fraudulently incorporated a non-existent cash component by inflating the bank balances, fudging bills, accounts receivables, interest and liabilities.

(Source: Compiled by author from Jones, M. (2011) 'Creative accounting, Fraud and International Accounting Standards,' John Wiley & Sons, London, page 235)

Satyam Computers Services Limited "Inflated cash and bank balances of more than \$1.5 billion (Rs. 7,000 crore), overstated debtors position of \$100 million and understated liability of \$250 million" was arranged for CEO Raju. Even though Satyam is not only the first major accounting scandal that India has seen, one of the release by the India Credit Rating Agency "CRISIL" seems to have sounded an alarm signal. This study is based on the analysis of 639 companies. Of these, as many as 226 companies (forming 33.33%) of the universe were found to be inflated their profit and 21.91% deflated their position through clever, though legal accounting practices. Even though banks and financial institutions are unhappy with the existing accounting practices followed by their corporate borrowers, they are helpless in taking any legal action. Some of the prominent examples of corporate-sector from India having used CA practices, as reported are:

- **TELCO:** Capitalized Rs. 1.178 crore dinner party expenses instead of writing it off in the year 2001-02, showed only a modest loss of 53 crores instead of actual loss, which was very huge
- **Mahindra and Mahindra:** While developing and launching their new SUV passenger vehicle "Scorpio", Mahindra and Mahindra picked-up the hint and repeated the practices of Telco in the year 2002-03. On questioning the Telco spokespersons said that they have done no wrong legally. However CRISIL remarks says "ideally, we should have written off the amount against the profit and loss account over a period of time rather than against the reserves at one go"
- **ICICI Bank:** The ICICI wrote off Rs. 813 crore of bad loans against its profit and loss account in 2001, as a result profit fell by 55%. As against this, ICICI wrote-off only Rs. 701 crore in the three years 1997 to 1999 and that too against reserves. The one time write off in FY 2001, prior to the ICICI Bank.
- **Reliance Petroleum Ltd. (RPL):** RPL showed the income earned from deferred sales tax as part of income. This practice is however, within the current accounting laws.

- **Rolta India:** Rolta India was accused off propping-up its sales in the late 1990s and early years of 20th century by adopting some creative method of accounting. The company has been accused of inflating its sales by asking one of its divisions to sell capital equipment to another on profit.
- **HDFC bank** has been showing profits from sale of investments as part of operating profit. During FY 2002, about 4% of such profits came from sale of securities.

Most of the examples cited above are from the “cream of Indian companies”. And even they hide expenses and prop-up incomes with a view to posting better profits and inflating their “profitability”, without violating accounting rules and conventions. Management of the firms could “indulge in the above-mentioned practices because of the flexibility in accounting standards and other regulatory provisions, thus, leading to CA and fraudulent accounting practices.” The best thing about the Satyam episode, as far as investors are concerned, is that it forced more companies to clean up their account books and governance practices. As Mampatta and Shrivastava (2010) remarked, “The year after the Satyam Computer Services fiasco came to light, corporations were less inclined to indulge in “CA.” With the stocks of companies perceived to be flouting prudent CG practices—particularly real-estate companies—taking a beating, India Inc. had little choice but to take notice. In a report, Noble Group (a UK-based investment bank) has evaluated the accounting practices for 313 BSE 500 companies. In fact, 63 BSE 500 financial services sector companies were excluded because they do not lend themselves to the ‘forensic accounting’ techniques used and 124 companies were excluded because their ‘consolidated’ financial statements for the past two financial years were not available.

According to Nobel Research Report (2009), “We estimates that 20% of India’s top 500 companies indulge in CA/EM malpractices, such as recording revenue ahead of time, booking fictitious sales, and manipulated cash figures. We find that the incidence of ‘Creative Accounting’ has abated in 2008-09, as compared to the previous financial year. This could be due to the corporation’s apprehensions after Satyam fiasco. This could be because of companies and auditors taking fright following the Satyam scam. It could also be that in a bear- market year (like 2008-09), when all the stocks were hammered globally, corporation’s incentive to flout the accounting rules were muted,” says Saurabh Mukherjea, head (Indian equities), Noble Group (Raj, 2010). Unfortunately, this means that as more companies look at tapping the market, the holier-than-thou act that India Inc. has been putting up may be on its way out. If the ‘incentive’ to “cook-books” is indeed back, investors need to be more careful.

The sectors where the CA was the most popular in 2007-08 were, as shown in **Table 2**, housing (including firms related to real-estate, construction and cement), information technology, and capital goods (such as companies in construction, power T&D and materials). In 2008-09, there was a shake-up in the defaulter list. The health-care sector replaced the IT-sector among the worst performers. Also, the top 50 stocks in the BSE 500 (by market capitalization) were the most likely segment of the market to have a company in Noble’s Creative Accounting “blacklist of the 50 worst companies” for 2008-09. Moreover, the family-controlled groups also switch funds between their companies for personal gain or to improve their stock prices. Many family promoters compromise the interests of shareholders in pursuit of immediate personal wealth accumulation. Check out the consolidated annual statements that a company provides. Pay particular attention to revenue, expense and cash pilferage, the three most common ways of manipulating accounts. Meanwhile, the “forensic accounting business remains a growth segment, growing at 40-50 percent a year.”

Table 2: Industry Sectors Using Creative Accounting in India

Sector	Per cent of 50 worst companies	Probability of fudging books (in per cent)
Housing-related	16	25
Healthcare	12	21
Capital goods	10	14
Metal, metal products and mining	10	21
Information technology	8	12

(Source: Raj, Rakesh (2010), "BSE's Top 50 may be Worst at Accounting," *Business Today*, January 21, 2010).

A July 2014 report, prepared by India Ratings (a credit assessor), points to the poor quality of FS(s) prepared by the publicly-listed companies in India, with "significant likelihood that companies in the top-100 of BSE 500 companies could be involved in Creative Accounting (CA) practices (Livemint, 2015). The figure comes from the study of the financial data of 421 companies over 12 years." Among all, the pharmaceutical, automobile and packaged consumer goods sectors remain most prone to the malice of accounting gimmickry. Under-reporting tax liabilities, depreciation and other costs (such as, interest, selling & distribution expenses) are some of the techniques used to misreport actual costs; while channel pushing is a favorite tool to create illusory sales that boost revenue. The urge for companies to meet Street expectations is a crucial factor driving the adoption of CA practices, especially during economic downturns, when the pressure on earnings increases considerably. If the current accounting framework is restructured and strict adherence to CG guidelines is ensured, then practices of CA can be curbed.

Review of Empirical Studies

Shah (1998) tried to explore the environment of CA in the UK, focusing on the motivations and constraints on such practices, by examining the accounting practices of two UK companies which issued creative financing instruments. He found that CA is influenced by two key motivators: stakeholder contracts and performance indicators. Amat et al. (1999, 2003) have reported on surveys of auditors' perceptions of CA in the UK, Spain and New Zealand to investigate the ethical issues raised by CA. It was revealed in their studies that the aggregate impact of CA practices on earnings amounted 20% of total reported earnings. They found that New Zealand offered an example of a country where a well-designed framework of accounting regulation has curbed CA. Similarly, Baralexis (2004) investigated "why, how, to what extent, and in what direction, CA was practiced in Greece. Knezevic et al., (2012) used a questionnaire to conduct a study of companies in Serbia. Two studies by Laura and Ileana (2013), and Balaciu et al., (2014) are based on the administration of a questionnaire to Romanian companies and managers using projective technique. A study by Momani and Obeidat (2013) investigated the effect of audit ethics on auditors' ability to detect the practices of CA in Jordan.

In Turkey, Kucukkocaoglu and Kucuksozen (2005) aimed "to detect manipulated financial statements of firms listed in Istanbul Stock Exchange by using logistic regression model." Moreover, Bayirli (2006) has focused on the scope, incentive factors, limits, practice methods and results of CA in Turkey. In order to determine the CA practices of Turkish firms, he used accruals method and used modified Jones model by adding country specific variables. Similarly, Omurgonulsen and Omurgonulsen (2009) have "examined the CA practices in Imarbank, which is one of the recent banking scandals in Turkey, using case study methodology."

Osazevaru (2012) investigated the effect of CA on firm value in Nigeria, and the findings of the study revealed that it can positively affect firm's value. Another study, which also focused on Nigeria, is by Idris et al. (2012). Using survey method, they investigated the practice of CA, its nature, techniques, and prevention. They concluded that "one of the best ways to prevent the practice of CA is to enforce both preventive as well as strong enough punitive measures on those that engage in the practice." Similarly, Sansusi and Izedonmi (2014) made an empirical investigation on the opinions of experienced staff of commercial banks on CA practices in

Nigerian commercial banks. They recommended that “CA should be considered as a serious crime and as such accounting bodies, law courts and other regulatory authorities need to adopt strict measures to stop the practice.” Moreover, Micah and Chinwe (2014) have used survey data and financial reports on 14 manufacturing firms over 5 year period to “examine whether CA and organizational effectiveness has any significant relationship.” Recently, the study by Blessing (2015) evaluated the use of forensic accounting techniques in curbing CA.

Bhasin (2013) examined the India’s Enron, Satyam Computers Creative Accounting scandal. He suggested “the increasing rate of white-collar crimes demands stiff penalties, exemplary punishments, and effective enforcement of law with the right spirit.” Moreover, Soral and Kamra (2013) explored the ethical and unethical aspects of CA with the help of cases from India and abroad. Similarly, Rajput (2014) found that CA exists due to lack of awareness and information level of investors. He highlighted the role of government and various agencies like SFIO and India Forensic for proper handling of the problem of CA.

Renu and Aggarwal (2014) highlighted the CA in negative sense with the help of CA methods adopted by Enron Company and Satyam Computers, which led to the collapse of both of them. Yadav (2014) discussed the various aspects related to CA. He found that “the CA practices increase when managers want to boost the profit in case of unsuitable situation and suggested that such practices can be minimized by good corporate governance practices.” Patnaik et al., (2014) made an empirical analysis by undertaking a survey in some selected private sector undertakings in Kolkota, Bhubaneswar and Cuttack. They used questionnaire and Likert scale method and concluded that “window dressing practices are prevalent in majority of corporations and external auditors encourage such practices for their own interest.” Recently, Tassadaq and Malik (2015) in their empirical study collected the data through structured questionnaire from industrial sector of Pakistan. They concluded that “a company is involved in frauds or scandals because of several factors like unethical behaviors, agency problem and non-professional attitude.”

The above highlighted reviewed studies are focusing on different dimensions of the CA. So far, unfortunately, no detailed research study has been undertaken specifically in the Indian corporate sector context. The discussion-based model has been used on the basis of past references and experiences.

Research Methodology

CA is one of the most important accounting techniques used by the corporate-sector across the world, and one of the best methods to play with the accounting numbers. The CG also plays an important role in exercising a counter-check on the CA practices. As a result, we have taken the “qualitative approach” for this research study, and employed “questionnaire-based empirical survey research methodology.” In fact, this study is an “exploratory one, which has benefited from the primary and secondary sources of information.” The population of this study comprised of both the preparers’ and users’ of corporate FS(s), as well as, University teachers of accounting. Accordingly, a random sample of 120 people was selected, to whom the questionnaires were administered in 2013-14, out of which 85 were returned. Majority of them were found to be substantially complete and usable, and hence, analyzed giving an effective response rate of 70%. In fact, the current study posed 14 research questions to the participants, which were grouped under 7 sub-heads. They sought to find out the view-point and opinion of the preparers’ and users’ of the FS(s). However, the 5-point “Likert rating-scale was adopted for coding the response and mapping them into numeric values.”

In order to ‘design’ our research instrument, “We identified the select key variables of interest from the past literature, and arrange them sequentially to form a fully ‘structured’ questionnaire.” The questionnaire covered total of 14 questions, which covered different dimensions of the CA practices prevalent in the Indian corporate-

sectors financial reporting system. Finally, descriptive statistics for 14 questions posed to participants is used to find out the percentage and frequency of responses given by them.

Findings and Analysis of data

Indeed, the CA practices are at the root of a number of accounting scandals in the world leading to total loss of corporate image and executive integrity. Some practitioners and academicians see the CA practice as an illegal act, while others consider it as a legal act. Thus, the first set of questions asked to all the participant is: “(a) To what extent, do you think, the CA practices affect the financial reporting system; (b) In your opinion, what is the legal standing of the CA practices in financial reporting system?” Answer given by the participant is presented in **Table 3**. It very clearly highlights that 45(or 52.95%) participants “Strongly Agree”, 20(23.52%) simply “Agree”, 15(17.65%) were “Undecided”, 4(4.70%) “Disagree” and 1(1.18%) “Strongly Disagree” with the first question. Thus, it is very much clear that a large majority 65(76.47%) participants “Strongly Agree and Agree” that CA practices adversely affects the financial reporting system in the Indian corporate-sector.

In the next sub-question, we asked very categorically asked the participants, “In your opinion, what is the legal standing of the CA practices used by the company’s in their financial reporting system?” Considerably large number of participants 32(37.60%), consider CA practices to be “Legal” and “Totally Legal” and 14(16.50%) were neutral by saying “Don’t Know”. In sharp contrast, highest number of 39(45.90%) participants consider CA practices to be “Totally Illegal” and “Illegal”, respectively. Thus, in order to overcome the unethical and illegal standing of CA practice, several reform measures for the companies’ CG systems were imposed in India.

Table 3: Extent of Effect and Legal Standing of CA Practices on the Financial Reporting System

Answer	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Is CAP Affecting FS?		
Strongly Agree	45	52.95
Agree	20	23.52
Undecided	15	17.65
Disagree	04	4.70
Strongly Disagree	01	1.18
Is CAP Legal?		
Legal	12	14.10
Totally Legal	20	23.50
Don’t know	14	16.50
Totally Illegal	24	28.23
Illegal	15	17.67
Total	85	100.00

Sometimes managers manipulate FS(s) to influence certain competitors on the capital market. To get benefits from top management, managers are frequently tempted to show higher profits, which, very often, lead to adopting CA tactics. The second group of question asked to the participant is: “(a) In your opinion, who is the main manipulator of CA techniques under the corporate financial reporting system?; (b) Under the prevailing environment of galloping number and magnitude of scams and frauds, do you trust the FS(s) in view of the CA practices?” The response given by the participants is summarized in **Table 4**.

When the participants were very categorically asked, “Who, do you think, is the main manipulator of the CA techniques in the corporate financial reporting system,” 24(28.23%) participants declared “Accountants”, 36(42.35%) feel it to be “Managers”, 14(16.45%) thought it to be “Auditors”, whereas 11(12.94%) said that “CEOs” are primarily the main manipulators of CA techniques. As was expected under the present corporate

environment, very large number of participants, 60(70.58%), feel both the “Accountant and Managers” are the main hero’s to perpetuate the CA practices in the corporate sector FS(s).

On the other hand, when the participants of this study were asked that do you trust the FS(s) in view of the widespread use of the CA practices, 33(38.81%) were of the opinion that information contained in the FS(s) are “Completely Trustworthy” and” Trustworthy”, 42(49.43%) regards it as “Completely Untrustworthy” and “Untrustworthy”. Unfortunately, a very small segment 10(11.76%) appears to be confused, not sure/neutral, simply by saying “Don’t Know”.

Table 4: Key Manipulators and Trust of Financial Reporting System under CA Practices

Answer	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Who Manipulates FS?		
Accountant	24	28.23
Manager	36	42.35
Auditor	14	16.48
CEOs	11	12.94
Do You Trust FS?		
Completely Trustworthy	10	11.76
Trustworthy	23	27.05
Don’t know	10	11.76
Untrustworthy	14	16.49
Completely Untrustworthy	28	32.94
Total	85	100.00

A company is supposed to employ procedures that are “objective and conservative” but in practice, management may have many “competing motivations” that drives their choice of accounting policies, which influence their periodic estimates. Thus, CA is the purposeful intervention in the external financial reporting process, with the intent of obtaining some “private gain”. In our third set of our research question, we especially asked the participants: “(a) What, do you think, is the most important reason for using the CA practices in the financial reporting system?; (b) Do you think, it is easy to detect the CA practices in the financial reporting system?” The answer given by the participants to this question is summarized in **Table 5**.

When the participants were asked about the most important purpose for use of CA practice in the financial reporting system, 20(2.52%) participants identified it to “Strong Competition”; 29 (34.10%) to “Benefit to the Manipulator”, 26(30.60%) to “Need to Chase Investment”, and 10(11.78%) to the view that “Statement Making incorporating CA is an Art”. To sum up, 75(88.22%) participants, being the largest segment, were very much sure about the special “lead-role” played by the corporate management: benefit to manipulator, encounter competition, and attract capital investments, respectively.

Moreover, when the participants were asked about ease of detection of CA techniques in the corporate financial reporting system, a very large section of the participants 50(58.80%) were of the opinion that it is “Hard” and “Very Hard to Detect” the CA practices in the corporate FS(s). As against this, 25(29.40%) participants were of the opinion that it is “Easy” and “Very Easy to Detect”, and 10(11.80%) were not clear and appeared to be confused; they gave the reason “Don’t Know”.

Table 5: Purpose and Ease of Detection of the CA Practices in Financial Statements

Answer	Frequency	Percentage (%)
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Why CAP is Used?		
Strong Competition	20	23.52
Benefits to Manipulator	29	34.10
Chase Investment	26	30.60
Art of Making FS	10	11.78
Is CAP Easy to Detect in FS?		
Very easy	09	10.58
Easy	16	18.82
Don't know	10	11.80
Hard	25	29.40
Very Hard	25	29.40
Total	85	100.00

Let us move to the fourth set of questions, “(a) To what extent, do you feel, the CA practices influence accounting policy choice and manipulation of transactions in the corporate financial reporting system?; and (b) Can you tell us, based on your experience, the most commonly used CA method for doing manipulation in the FSs?” The answer given by the participants for both questions shown is shown in **Table 6**.

An overwhelming majority of 75 participants (representing 88.24% of the sample-size), “Strongly Agree” and “Agree” with the statement contained in the second question. However, a small section of 7(8.24%) participants were “Undecided”, 3(3.52%) “Disagree”, while there was no participant who “Strongly Disagree” with the question posed to them. In short, only 10 participants out of our sample-size of 85 participants, representing 11.78% of the sample-size “Disagree” and “Undecided” (or in “Disagreement”) with the above stated question asked to them.

Moreover, when the participants were very categorically asked, “In your opinion, what is the most commonly used method under CA for doing manipulation in the financial statements,” highest number of participants, 32(37.65%), were of the opinion that mostly manipulation is done in the “off balance-sheet financing”, 20(23.52%) were of the opinion by “Making Changes in the Depreciation Policies and methods”, 10(11.78%) feel the manipulation is done in the “Extraordinary Items” and 21(24.70%) by making changes in the “Valuation of Money”. However, 2(2.35%) participants gave “Other Reasons” for manipulation in financial reporting system. Thus, from the above, there appears to be lack of consensus on the part of participants regarding the manipulation methodology used in CA practices in the Indian corporate sector. This may also be equally valid in other countries.

Table 6: Extent of CA Practices Affecting Accounting Policy Choice and Manipulation under Financial Reporting System

Answer	Frequency	Percentage (%)
CAP & Accounting Policy Selection:		
Strongly Agree	50	58.83
Agree	25	29.41
Undecided	7	8.24
Disagree	3	3.52
Strongly Disagree	--	--
What is Popular CA Manipulation Method?		
Off Balance Sheet Financing	32	37.65
Changes in Depreciation Policy	20	23.52
Extraordinary and Exceptional Items	10	11.78
Money Valuation	21	24.70
Others	02	2.35
Total	85	100.00

As part of this study, we posed the fifth set of question to our participants, as: “(a) To what extent, do you think, a well-designed framework of accounting regulation by the regulatory agencies in India, will help to curb the spread of CA practices in the corporate financial reporting system?; (b) What, do you think, is the role of ethical values in reducing the CA practices?.” The answer given by the participants, for both question, is summarized in **Table 7**.

It shows that a large majority of 59(69.41%) participants “Strongly Agree”, while 19(22.36%), “Agree” that a well-designed framework of accounting regulation by the regulatory agencies in India will help to curb the spread of CA practices in the corporate financial reporting system. However, just 7(8.23%) participants, a very small segment of the sample-size, are “Undecided”. Keeping in view the fraudulent reporting scenario prevalent in the Indian, as well as, global corporate sector, and as per our expectations, there is no respondent who “Disagree”, and also non who “Strongly Disagree” with the above stated question posed to them.

Similarly, when we asked the participants about the role of ethical values in controlling the use of CA techniques in FS(s), an overwhelming majority of 61(71.77%) participants “Strongly Agree” and “Agree” that ethical values can help, to a large extent, to reduce and control the negative CA practices prevalent in the Indian Corporate sector. However, a minor section of 10(11.76%) participants “Disagree”, and there was no participants, who “Strongly Disagree”. Unfortunately, 14(16.47%) were “Undecided” and hence, not able to make up their mind regarding the role played by the ethics/ethical values to reduce the CA practices prevalent in the Indian corporate sector.

Table 7: Extent of Accounting Regulation and Role of Ethical Values to Curb CA Practices

Answer	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Do We Need More Accounting Regulation?		
Strongly Agree	59	69.41
Agree	19	22.36
Undecided	7	8.23
Disagree	--	--
Strongly Disagree	--	--
What is Role of Ethical Values to Curb CA?		
Strongly Agree	35	41.17
Agree	26	30.60
Undecided	14	16.47
Disagree	10	11.76
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	85	100

It is widely accepted that rampant prevalent of the CA practices in the corporate world is “like an ‘incurable’ cancer, which is spreading very fast,” and it is therefore, not possible to totally eliminate such unethical and illegal practices. However, efforts should be made by all groups to minimize, at least, the negative effects of them by adopting the accounting standards, giving more importance to ethical considerations, and decreasing the flexibility of the managers in deciding among different accounting methods. In view of this, accordingly, we asked sixth group question to our participants: (a) Do you think, the auditor comments given in his audit reports are important and trustworthy?; (b) What do you feel about the role played by the government regulations to prevent and control the CA practices? The answer provided by the participant is briefly summarized in **Table 8**.

In response to our question to the participants regarding the importance and trust worthiness of the auditors' comments, as given in their audit report, a large majority of 54(63.52%) think it is "Completely Trustworthy" and "Trustworthy" and 24(28.26%) expressed their strong mistrust by saying it is totally "Untrustworthy" and "Completely Untrustworthy", respectively. As it is the normal practice, 7(8.23%) participants were "Undecided" about the trust worthiness of the auditors' comments given in his Audit Report.

Similarly, when the participants were especially asked about the importance of the role played by the various government regulatory agencies in India so as to prevent the abuse of CA practices, large majority of 55(64.70%) participants felt that various governmental agencies as regulators are "Very essential" and they play "Very Important" role, 15(17.66%) were of the opinion that such agencies are "Less Important" and "Not Important" (viz., governmental regulators do not play any important role and hence, irrelevant/not relevant), and 15(17.64%) felt that government regulations play a "Medium Importance" (or Moderate Important) role in preventing the CA practices in the corporate sector.

Table 8: Role of Auditors' Comments and Government Regulations to Control CA Practices

Answer	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Should We Trust Auditor Comments?		
Completely Trustworthy	21	24.70
Trustworthy	33	38.82
Undecided	07	8.23
Untrustworthy	18	21.19
Completely Untrustworthy	06	7.06
Do We Need More Govt. Regulations?		
Very Essential	34	40.00
Very Important	21	24.70
Medium Importance	15	17.64
Less Important	10	11.77
Not Important	05	5.89
Total	85	100.00

The business failures of the past four decades have been closely associated with "Corporate Governance (CG)" failure, which very often involve a number of parties: senior-level managers, board of directors, auditors, and some institutional investors. Keeping in mind this fragile scenario, finally, we asked the participants of this study our last set of questions, as: (a) In your opinion, what is the role and usefulness of various international/local accounting, audit and CG standards in preventing the CA practices in the corporate sector?; (b) Keeping in view your professional qualification, specialization, and rich work-experience, what would you like to recommend or suggest to us, as a broad guide, in order to reduce the frequent use of negative CA practices in the corporate world? The answer provided by the participants for both question is presented in **Table 9**.

In response to our question about the usefulness of international accounting, audit and CG standards in controlling and reducing the CA practices, an overwhelming majority, 60(70.60%) were of the opinion that they are pretty "Useful" and "Very Much Useful", respectively. As against this, there were in all 13(15.29%) participants, who were of the totally opposite opinion that various International Standards (comprising of accounting, auditing and Corporate Governance) are all "Useless" and "Totally Useless", respectively. However, a small segment of 12(14.11%) participants, once again, appears to be totally confused, and accordingly, they were not sure about their usefulness by saying "Don't Know".

In response to our question posed to participants, “Keeping in view your professional qualification, specialization, and rich work-experience, what would you like to recommend or suggest to us, as a broad guide, in order to reduce the frequent use of negative CA practices in the corporate world? An overwhelming majority 55(64.70%) of participants were of the opinion that “Effective Enforcement of Laws” and “Induct Independent External Directors” in the corporate sector are two possible solutions to control the misuse of CA practice in corporate financial reporting system. However, 20(23.52%) participants were of the opinion that the corporations must strengthen their “Internal Audit” system under the overall guidance and supervision of the Corporate Audit Committee, as part of CG Mechanism. As against this, 10(11.78%) participants were of the opinion that “Overhaul of External Audit” system should be undertaken by the Big Audit consultancy firms, by reviewing their audit standards, procedure followed and inducting ethical considerations on their professionals. This kind of division of opinion among the participants is quite natural, and is in line with the several research studies on similar topic reported in the past.

Table 9: Usefulness of International Standards and Suggestions for Controlling CA Practices

Answer	Frequency	Percentage (%)
What is Usefulness of International Standards?		
Useful	26	30.60
Very much Useful	34	40.00
Don't know	12	14.11
Totally Useless	10	11.77
Useless	03	3.52
How to Reduce CAP?		
Improve Internal Audit	20	23.52
Overhaul External Audit Effective enforcement of laws	10	11.78
Induct Independent Directors	32	37.65
	23	27.05
Total	85	100.00

Moving away from the top-echelon of management team and Board of Directors’ structure to audit, we believe that “an independent and powerful Audit Committee has to play very crucial role in discouraging the CA practices in the corporate world.” As we know, the great financial scandals were based on accounting manipulation practices, but also on collaborations with the audit firms, which instead of acting as the ‘guardians’ of the financial markets have come to overlook, to hide, and even to participate to some of the greatest frauds in the history. Thus, reform measures for the companies’ CG systems were also imposed. It was equally revealed that one of the best ways to prevent the practice of CA is “to enforce both preventive, as well as, strong enough punitive measures on those that engage in CA practice.” It was also recommended that “effective rules and regulation of accounting, audit and CG practices should be put in places within the corporate-sector to forestall the incidence of CA. Also, we recommend that “GAAP usage should be subjected to basic Statement of Audit and International Accounting Standards. Moreover, strong punitive measures should be promptly taken against those executives/managers found culpable in the act of CA.

Conclusion and Recommendations

CA is a term used to refer to the aggressive use of choices available under accounting rules, to present the most fattening view of a company in its FS(s). They seek loopholes in financial reporting standard, which they can exploit to adjust the numbers, as much as is practicable, to achieve their desired aim, satisfy their financial projections, or obtain some private gain. By and large, the effect of accounting manipulation can be disastrous leading to a total loss of corporate image and executive integrity. The accuracy and reliability of the FS(s) are

crucial for the stakeholders of the firms in order to make appropriate decisions (Susmus, 2013). Sometimes, the CA practices has been compared with the incurable cancer, behind this new face of crime in the land involving the cooking or roasting of FS(s), and conventional audit has been totally inadequate in handling it. The accounting profession seems not to have realized the stigma this is causing to their profession ((Ijeoma and Aronu, 2015)). If there are carefully articulated and professionally executed control schemes of an accounting, auditing and investigative nature would it not have put a stop to these irregular financial practices, which has fostered unexpected strains and hiccups in the economy globally? Should not the accounting profession accept more responsibilities and get the possibilities of arresting this cancerous situation in the economy? Everyone is affected, one way or the other, by this dilemma; is it not high time the accountants sought for a financial messiah?

This study revealed that the practice of CA is an attempt to gain advantage of a form to the managers and companies. Also, it shows that the current GAAP create a gap that can permit and encourage the practice of CA. However, we are of the opinion that the International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) will go a long-way to reduce the CA practice, since it covers more areas than the former practice. It was equally revealed that one of the best ways to prevent the practice of CA is to enforce both preventive as well as strong enough punitive measures on those that engage in CA practice. It was recommended that effective rules and regulation of accounting practice should be put in places within the organization to forestall the incidence of CA. Also, it was recommended that GAAP usage should be subjected to basic SAS and IAS standards. We recommend that “the scope for choice of accounting methods be reduced by reducing the number of permitted accounting methods, thus specifying circumstances in which each method should be used. Also, we believe that the abuse of judgment can be reduced by drafting rules that minimize the use of judgment and prescribe consistency so that if a company chooses an accounting policy that suits it in one year, it will be forced to use the same method in future circumstances where the result may be less favorable.” Moreover, auditors should have a part to play in identifying and reporting dishonest estimates, and they should be given the responsibility of detecting and reporting all instances of CA practices. It is recommended that accounting rules and regulations should be strictly adopted by companies so that no one can get any advantage of the existing loopholes of accounting framework, otherwise strict legal action must be taken. This may ensure, “true and fair view” of the financial statements.

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